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Research Article

Identification and Quantification of Flavonoids in *Musa Paradisiaca* by Using Colorimetric Method

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ABSTRACT

Musa paradisiaca, a widely distributed medicinal plant, is known for its diverse pharmacological properties, including antimicrobial, anti-cancer, anti-oxidant, anti-diabetic, anti-inflammatory, and wound healing effects. The presence of bioactive flavonoids contributes significantly to its therapeutic potential. This study aims to determine and quantify the flavonoids content in *musa paradisiaca* leaves using a colorimetric method. Flavonoids were extracted using soxhlet extraction techniques, and their concentration was measured colorimetrically. The absorbance was recorded at a specific wavelength of 450nm, and a calibration curve was established using a standard rutin. The results indicated 6.2% of flavonoids in the leaf extract, demonstrating the potential of *Musa paradisiaca* as a source of bioactive compounds. This study provides a simple, cost effective, and reliable method for flavonoids quantification, which could be useful for further pharmacological studies.

INTRODUCTION

A colorimeter is a device that is used in Colorimetry. It refers to a device which helps specific solutions to absorb a particular wavelength of light. The colorimeter is usually used to measure the concentration of a known solute in a given solution with the help of the Beer-Lambert law.

The colorimeter was invented in the year 1870 by Louis J Duboscq.

Principle of Colorimeter

It is a photometric technique which states that when a beam of incident light of intensity I_0 passes through a solution, the following occur:

- A part of it is reflected which is denoted as I_r
- A part of it is absorbed which is denoted as I_a

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- Rest of the light is transmitted and is denoted as I_t

Therefore, $I_o = I_r + I_a + I_t$ To determine I_a the measurement of I_o and I_t is sufficient therefore, I_r is eliminated. The amount of light reflected is kept constant to measure I_o and I_t .

- Simple and Easy to Use - Requires minimal training and is straightforward in operation.
- Quick Results - Provides rapid and reliable measurements.
- Cost-Effective - More affordable compared to spectrophotometers.

Advantages of Colorimeter:

Disadvantages of Colorimeter:

- Limited to Colored Solutions - Cannot analyze colorless solutions or gases effectively.
- Less Precise Than Spectrophotometers - Not suitable for highly accurate broad-spectrum analysis.
- Affects by Turbidity and Impurities - Suspended particles can interfere with the accuracy of results.

MATERIALS:

Musa paradisiaca leaves, Ethanol, Rutin, Sodium nitrite, Aluminium chloride, Sodium hydroxide, Petroleum glycol, Distilled water.

Apparatus:

Soxhlet apparatus, RBF, Condenser, Whatman filter paper, Spatula, Funnel, Tripod stand, Measuring cylinder, Filter paper, Beaker, Volumetric flask (10ml,100ml), Glass rod, Pipette, Test tubes, Cuvettes.

Instruments:

Digital balance, Colorimeter, Heating mantle.

Plant Collection:

The collected fresh leaves of *Musa paradisiaca* were washed and dried in shade. After drying plant leaves were finely powdered and kept in a well closed container. For further extraction procedure.

Method Of Extraction:

Soxhlet method: 30 grams of finely powdered *Musa paradisiaca* leaves are packed in a thimble and placed in the sample holder. And pour 350 ml

of ethanol into it. Extraction was carried out for 12 hr at 80°C. Later on, the extract was filtered, and the filtrate was stored for further use.

Phytochemical Screening

Identification Test for Alkaloids:

Test	Procedure	Observation
1. Dragendorff Test	Take 2 ml extract and add 2ml of dragendorff reagent to it.	A orange red precipitate was formed. It indicates the presence Alkaloids.
2. Hager's Test	Take 2 ml extract and add 2 drops of aqueous picric acid solution.	A creamy white precipitate was not formed. It indicates the absence of alkaloids.

Dragendorff's test

Identification Tests for Flavanoids:

Test	Procedure	Observation

1. Ferric chloride test	Take 2ml extract and add Ferric chloride solution to it.	Greenish black colour was formed which indicates the presence of Flavonoids.
2. Alkaline reagent test	Add few drops of sodium hydroxide to a test solution.	Yellow colour was formed which indicates the absence of flavonoids.

Ferric chloride test

Identification Test for Carbohydrates:

Dragendorff's test

Identification Tests for Flavanoids:

Test	Procedure	Observation
1.Ferric chloride test	Take 2ml extract and add Ferric chloride solution to it.	Greenish black colour was formed which indicates the presence of Flavanoids.
2.Alkaline reagent test	Add few drops of sodium hydroxide to a test solution.	Yellow colour was formed which indicates the absence of flavonoids.

Ferric Chloride Test

Identification Test for Carbohydrates:

Test	Procedure	Observation
1.Molisch's test	Take 2ml extract and add αnaphthol and few drops of concentrated H ₂ SO ₄ .	A purple ring was formed at the point of contact between the acidic and which indicates the presence of carbohydrates.
2.Fehling's test	Take 2ml of extract and add equal quantities of Fehling's A &B solutions.	A brick red precipitate was formed which indicates the presence of carbohydrates.

Fehling's test

Molisch's test

Identification Test for Terpinoids

Salkowski Test

Test	Procedure	Observation
1. Salkowski test	Take 5ml extract and add 2ml chloroform and evaporate on water bath then add 3ml concentrated H ₂ SO ₄ .	Reddish brown interface was formed which indicates the presence of terpenoids.

Method Of Preparation:

- ❖ **Preparation of Rutin solution:**
- Accurately weighed 1 gm of Rutin and added to 100 ml volumetric flask.

S. No	Wavelength (Nm)	Concentration (Mg/MI)	Absorbance
1.	450nm	1mg/ml	0.47
2.	470nm	1mg/ml	0.41
3.	510nm	1mg/ml	0.21
4.	520nm	1mg/ml	0.09
5.	540nm	1mg/ml	0.04
6.	570nm	1mg/ml	0.22
7.	600nm	1mg/ml	0.02
8.	670nm	1mg/ml	0.01

Preparation Of Calibration Curve:

- Added 30 ml of ethanol into it to dissolve and make up the volume to 100 ml.
- ❖ **Preparation of sodium hydroxide solution:**
- Accurately weighed 4 gms of NaOH and added to 100 ml volumetric flask.
- Added 30 ml of distilled water into it to dissolve and make up the volume to 100 ml.
- ❖ **Preparation of sodium nitrite:**
- Accurately weighed 5 gms of sodium nitrite and added to 100 ml volumetric flask.
- Added 30 ml of distilled water into it to dissolve and make up the volume to 100 ml.
- ❖ **Preparation of Aluminium chloride:**
- Accurately weighed 10 gm of AlCl₃ and added to 100 ml volumetric flask.
- Added 30 ml of distilled water into it to dissolve and make up the volume to 100 ml.

Selection Of Wavelength:

- ❖ For 1 ml of Rutin solution 10 ml volumetric flask.
- ❖ Make up the volume to 10 ml.
- ❖ Measure the absorbance of the above solution at different wavelengths. (450 nm, 470 nm, 510 nm, 520 nm, 540 nm, 570 nm, 600 nm and 670 nm) against blank.
- **The maximum absorbance is at 450 nm - λ_{max} is 450 nm**

- Five different concentrations (0.2 mg, 0.4 mg, 0.6 mg, 0.8 mg, and 1.0 mg) of rutin were taken from standard 1 mg/ml Rutin in five different 10 ml volumetric flasks.

- Added 0.3ml of 5% NaNo₂ and 0.3ml of 10% AlCl₃ and 2ml of 0.4 % NaoH solution.
- Then keep it for 6min.
- Make up the volume with distilled water upto the mark.
- The solution was keep it for 15 mins at room temperature.
- The absorbance was measured at 450nm.

S. No	Wavelength (Nm)	Concentration (Mg)	Absorbance
1.	450nm	0.2	0.18
2.	450nm	0.4	0.31
3.	450nm	0.6	0.47
4.	450nm	0.8	0.56
5.	450nm	1.0	0.73

Procedure For Determination of Extract

- 0.2ml of plant extract was taken in a10ml volumetric flask
- Added 0.3ml of 5% NaNo₂ and 0.3ml of 10% AlCl₃ and 2ml of 4% NaoH solution.
- Then keep it for 6min.
- Makeup the volume with distilled water upto the mark.
- The solution was keep it for 15 mins at room temperature.
- Then the absorbance was measured at 450nm.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Calculation

S. No	Wavelength (Nm)	Concentration (Mg)	Absorbance
1.	450nm	0.2	0.18
2.	450nm	0.4	0.31
3.	450nm	0.6	0.47

4.	450nm	0.8	0.56
5.	450nm	1.0	0.73

FORMULA:

Concentration of flavonoid content in 30gms (450ml)

Concentration found \times Volume of final extract

Total flavonoid content = Quantity of extract taken

$$= \frac{0.83 \times 450}{0.2}$$

1867.5mg of rutin in 30gms of powder.

Concentration in 30gms

$$\% \text{ of flavonoids in 30gms} = \frac{\text{Concentration in 30gms}}{\text{Weight of powder}} \times 100 = \frac{1.8675}{30} \times 100 = 6.225\%$$

30 = 6.225%

The total flavonoid content in *Musaparadisiaca* leaves was found to be 6.225%

Summary

This study focuses on the identification and quantification of flavonoids content in *Musa paradisiaca* leaves using a colorimeter method. Flavonoids, known for their medicinal properties, were extracted using Soxhlet extraction technique. The quantification was performed by forming a colored complex and the absorbance was measured colorimetrically at 450nm. A standard calibration curve using known flavonoids (rutin) concentrations was used to determine the flavonoids content in the plant extract. The results confirmed **6.225% of** flavonoids in *Musa paradisiaca* leaves, supporting its potential for pharmaceutical applications. This

method provides a simple, cost effective, and reliable approach for flavonoids analysis, beneficial for quality control and further pharmacological research.

CONCLUSION

The colorimetric method used in this study successfully determined and quantified the flavonoid content in *Musaparadisiaca* leaves. The extraction and complexation provided are liable and cost-effective approach for Flavonoids analysis. The results confirmed a significant presence of flavonoids, highlighting the medicinal potential of *Musaparadisiaca*. This method can serve as a valuable tool for quality control in herbal formulations and further pharmacological research. Further studies can focus on optimizing the method for higher sensitivity and exploring the biological activities of the quantified Flavonoid's.

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